

D8.13

Press Releases 1

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Glossary, abbreviations, and acronyms

EN	English
ES	Spanish
GR	Greek
PT	Portuguese

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable entitled “Press releases” will contain all the press releases created by the BBTWINS project until the 30th of November and their translation into the local, national, and regional languages of the partners participating in this project.

Press releases are a tool to help communicate and disseminate the project to the media and the public, that can amplify the impact of the project by reaching a larger audience. The Consortium plans to distribute more new press releases when new results are published, or new dissemination materials are available.

Until now the project has launched one press release about the kick-off meeting of the project, released the 30th of September 2021 and can be found in four languages (English, Spanish, Portuguese, and Greek) in its full version and in Polish in a shorter version.

The press releases of the project are already be available on the website of the project (see <https://bbtwins.eu/press-releases/>). This area is regularly updated with new content as communication material is created.

This D8.13 is the first of a series of four deliverables including press releases of BBWTINS as follows:

- D8.13 Press Releases 1 / ZIC / Report / Public / M6
- D8.14 Press releases 3 / ZIC / Report / Public / M30
- D8.15 Press releases 2 / ZIC / Report / Public / M18
- D8.16 Press releases 4 / ZIC / Report / Public / M42

2. Press releases

Figure 1 Press release about the kick-off meeting in EN

Figure 2 Press release about the kick-off meeting in EN

PRESS RELEASE

Keywords

Digital twins, blockchain, logistics, biomass valorisation, sensors, simulation, fertilizers, proteins, fruit processing, meat processing, feedstock, salts, protein, snacks, nutraceutical, waste, digital services, technology development, bioeconomy

About BBTWINS

Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) aims to develop a digital platform for the optimisation of agri-food value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for bioprocessing.

The platform will be based on 'digital twins' technology – creating a real-time digital replica of physical processes in the agri-food industry. BBTWINS will also combine Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, the Internet of Things (IoT) and software analytics in this single platform.

With 13 partners in 7 countries, the BBTWINS consortium will be focusing on meat and fruit production, integrating the value chain (from crop to final product) and will define the optimal pathway for each feedstock to maximise efficiency and minimise losses – without impacting quality.

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Figure 3 Press release about the kick-off meeting in EN

Nota de prensa

Los “Digital twins” prometen una mayor eficiencia de los recursos para el sector agroalimentario de la UE

El proyecto de BBTWINS Horizonte2020 aplicará tecnología de vanguardia para optimizar las cadenas de valor de la carne y la fruta

Bruselas, 30 de septiembre de 2021 – El sector agroalimentario de la UE es un elemento clave de la economía europea. Las pérdidas de las pequeñas empresas y las ineficiencias de este sector se acumulan, lo que supone una importante carga económica y medioambiental. [La agricultura es responsable de casi un tercio de todos los gases de efecto invernadero \(GEI\)](#) y, dado que se calcula que la población mundial alcanzará los 10.000 millones de habitantes en 2050, la eficiencia de los sistemas de producción agrícola y ganadera deben aumentar un 40% para satisfacer esta demanda. La tecnología de vanguardia representa una oportunidad para avanzar en la sostenibilidad del sector mediante el aumento de la eficiencia y la optimización de las cadenas de valor, ayudando a superar estos desafíos.

[BBTWINS](#), un proyecto de Acción de Investigación e Innovación en Industrias de Base Biológica que ha recibido 4,7 millones de euros con el objetivo de reformar el sector. El proyecto contribuirá a la [estrategia “de la granja a la mesa”](#) de la UE, un componente clave del [“Green Deal”](#) de la UE, mediante el desarrollo de “digital twins” o representaciones digitales de las cadenas de valor agrícolas para aumentar la eficiencia de los recursos, reducir los residuos y permitir un sector agroalimentario más resistente.

Coordinado por CTIC-CITA, BBTWINS se desarrollará durante cuatro años (2021-2025) con la colaboración de 13 socios de siete países distintos, entre los que se encuentran organizaciones de investigación,

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Figure 4 Press release about the kick-off meeting in ES

PRESS RELEASE

cooperativas, clústeres de bioeconomía y empresas, que trabajarán juntos para optimizar la cadena de valor alimentaria.

"La digitalización de los procesos de producción es una poderosa herramienta que nos permitirá simular diferentes escenarios en un ordenador para identificar las mejoras que realmente importan."

– Daniel de la Puente, Gestor de proyectos de la UE, CTIC-CITA

Las herramientas digitales innovadoras cubrirán casos de uso en España y Grecia, para la producción de cerdo y melocotón, respectivamente. Estas representaciones digitales seguirán un enfoque multiactor, integrando todas las etapas del proceso en una sola plataforma.

El trabajo sobre estos casos de uso seguirá un enfoque holístico, incluyendo una evaluación medioambiental, social y económica. El desarrollo integrará tecnologías como la inteligencia artificial (IA), el Internet de las Cosas (IoT) y el análisis de software, junto con blockchain y soluciones logísticas estratégicas, creando una clara representación de cómo optimizar las cadenas de valor completas.

BBTWINS apoyará la lucha de Europa contra el cambio climático mediante la creación de tecnologías reproducibles que mejoren la eficiencia agroalimentaria al tiempo que impulsan la bioeconomía de la UE.

ENDS

Figure 5 Press release about the kick-off meeting in ES

PRESS RELEASE

Keywords

Digital twins, blockchain, logistics, biomass valorisation, sensors, simulation, fertilizers, proteins, fruit processing, meat processing, feedstock, salts, protein, snacks, nutraceutical, waste, digital services, technology development, bioeconomy

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Figure 6 Press release about the kick-off meeting in ES

Press release

Centro de Investigação CVR ligado à tecnologia digital twins que promete revolucionar o setor agroalimentar da EU

O projeto BBTWINS irá aplicar tecnologia de ponta para otimizar as cadeias de valor das indústrias da carne e fruta

Bruxelas, 12 de outubro 2021 – O setor agroalimentar da UE é um dos principais contribuintes para a economia europeia. As perdas e ineficiências das pequenas empresas neste setor vão-se acumulando, resultando em significativos problemas económicos e ambientais. [A agricultura é responsável por quase um terço de todos os gases de efeito estufa](#) e com a população mundial estimada em 10 mil milhões até 2050, a eficiência do sistema de produção agrícola e pecuária deve aumentar em 40% para atender a esta demanda. A tecnologia de ponta apresenta uma oportunidade de avançar na sustentabilidade do setor ao aumentar a eficiência e a otimização das cadeias de valor, ajudando a superar esses desafios.

O [BBTWINS](#), um projeto de Ação de Pesquisa e Inovação de Bioindústrias, recebeu 4,7 milhões de euros com o objetivo de reformar o setor. O projeto contribuirá para a estratégia da quinta para o garfo (farm-to-fork) da União Europeia, um componente-chave do [Green Deal da UE](#), desenvolvendo digital twins ou representações digitais de cadeias de valor agrícola para aumentar a eficiência dos recursos, reduzir o desperdício e permitir que o setor agroalimentar se torne mais forte.

O CVR – Centro para a Valorização de Resíduos, Centro de Interface Tecnológico situado no Campus de Azurém da Universidade do Minho (UM), faz parte do consórcio de 13 entidades de sete países, sendo o único representante português. Com coordenação do CTIC-CITA, o BBTWINS será executado durante quatro anos (2021-2025).

1

Figure 7 Press release about the kick-off meeting in PT

PRESS RELEASE

A tecnologia digital twins vai cobrir casos práticos em Espanha e na Grécia, para produção de carne de porco e pêsego, respetivamente. Estes digital twins seguirão uma abordagem de vários intervenientes, integrando todas as etapas de processamento - do farm-to-fork - numa única plataforma.

“A introdução da abordagem de biorrefinaria de resíduo zero em setores tradicionais, como a produção de carne de porco e pêsego, será um grande passo em direção à sua sustentabilidade econômica, social e ambiental.”

“A introdução da abordagem de biorrefinaria de resíduos zero em setores tradicionais, como a produção de carne de porco e pêsego, será um grande passo em direção à sua sustentabilidade económica, social e ambiental.”

– André Ribeiro, Investigador Sénior, CVR – Centro para a Valorização de Resíduos

O trabalho nestes casos seguirá uma abordagem holística, incluindo uma avaliação ambiental, social e económica. Os digital twins desenvolvidos irão integrar tecnologias como inteligência artificial (IA), Internet of Things (IoT) e análise de software, juntamente com blockchain e soluções logísticas estratégicas - criando uma representação clara de como otimizar todas as cadeias de valor.

O BBTWINS apoiará a luta da Europa contra as alterações climáticas através da criação de tecnologias replicáveis que melhoram a eficiência agroalimentar, ao mesmo tempo que reforçam a bioeconomia da UE.

FIM

Figure 8 Press release about the kick-off meeting in PT

PRESS RELEASE

Keywords

Digital twins, blockchain, logística, valorização de biomassa, sensores, simulação, fertilizantes, fruta, carne, proteína, snack, resíduos, desperdício, bioeconomia, tecnologia

Sobre o BBTWINS

O projeto Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) tem como objetivo desenvolver uma plataforma digital para a otimização dos processos da cadeia de valor agroalimentar e o fornecimento de biomassa de qualidade para o bioprocessamento.

A plataforma será baseada na tecnologia de 'digital twins' - criando uma réplica digital em tempo real de processos físicos na indústria agroalimentar. O BBTWINS também combinará Inteligência Artificial (IA), Machine Learning, Internet of Things (IoT) e análise de software nesta plataforma única.

Com 13 parceiros em 7 países, o consórcio BBTWINS irá concentrar-se na produção de carne e frutas, integrando a cadeia de valor (do cultivo ao produto final) e definirá o caminho ideal para cada matéria-prima para maximizar a eficiência e minimizar as perdas - sem afetar a qualidade.

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Este projeto recebeu financiamento da Bio Based Industries (JU) ao abrigo do acordo de subvenção n.º 101023334. A JU recebe apoio do programa de investigação e inovação Horizonte 2020 da União Europeia e do Bio Based Industries Consortium.

Figure 9 Press release about the kick-off meeting in PT

BBTWINS: Πως θα γίνουν πιο αποτελεσματικά και παραγωγικά τα συστήματα παραγωγής τροφίμων, εν μέσω της αυξανόμενης ζήτησης παγκοσμίως

Το Cluster Βιοοικονομίας ΠΔΜ θα είναι ο κύριος εταίρος του έργου: «Ψηφιακά Δίδυμα για τη βελτιστοποίηση των διαδικασιών της αγροδιατροφικής αλυσίδας αξίας και την προμήθεια ποιοτικής βιομάζας για βιο-επεξεργασία»

Η Ευρωπαϊκή Ένωση, είναι ήδη ο μεγαλύτερος παραγωγός τροφίμων και ποτών στον κόσμο. Ωστόσο, καθώς αυξάνεται η ζήτηση για τρόφιμα, ο τομέας αυτός βρίσκεται υπό αυξανόμενη πίεση. Τα συστήματα παραγωγής τροφίμων πρέπει να γίνουν πιο αποτελεσματικά και παραγωγικά, παρέχοντας θρεπτικά, υγιεινά τρόφιμα σε μεγαλύτερες ποσότητες, ενώ ταυτόχρονα αντιμετωπίζουν την αυξανόμενη δημόσια ζήτηση για ελαχιστοποίηση τυχόν περιβαλλοντικών επιπτώσεων.

Η λύση σε αυτήν την πρόκληση θα βρεθεί εν μέρει μέσω της ανάπτυξης ψηφιακών λύσεων. Το έργο BBTWINS θα αναπτύξει μια ψηφιακή πλατφόρμα βασισμένη στη λεγόμενη τεχνολογία «ψηφιακού διδύμου». Δηλαδή τη διαδικασία να παραχθεί ένα ψηφιακό αντίγραφο σε πραγματικό χρόνο μιας φυσικής διαδικασίας που μπορεί να εξεταστεί, να τροποποιηθεί και να δοκιμαστεί χωρίς να αλληλεπιδρά με αυτήν στον πραγματικό κόσμο και να αποφεύγονται αρνητικές συνέπειες. Χρησιμοποιώντας δύο περιπτώσεις χρήσης – παραγωγή κρέατος και φρούτων – θα δείξει πώς να ενσωματώσει, σε μια μόνο αλυσίδα αξίας, τόσο ολόκληρη την αλυσίδα αξίας γεωργικών τροφίμων (από καλλιέργεια έως τελικό προϊόν) όσο και τις πρώτες ύλες που παράγονται σε όλα τα στάδια.

Αυτή η ψηφιακή διπλή προσέγγιση θα συνδυάσει τις σύγχρονες ψηφιακές τεχνολογίες, όπως η Τεχνητή Νοημοσύνη, η Μηχανική Μάθηση, το Internet of Things και τα αναλυτικά λογισμικά σε μία μόνο πλατφόρμα. Αυτή η πλατφόρμα θα είναι σε θέση να προβλέψει τη βέλτιστη προεπεξεργασία και διαδρομή για κάθε πρώτη ύλη υπό διαφορετικές συνθήκες. Με αυτόν τον τρόπο, θα αυξήσει τη διαθέσιμη βιομάζα, θα μειώσει τις απώλειες βιομάζας και θα αυξήσει τους χρόνους αποθήκευσης βιομάζας χωρίς να επηρεάσει την ποιότητα.

Το έργο BBTWINS, του οποίου η εναρκτήρια συνάντηση έγινε στις 22 και 23 Ιουνίου 2021, θα προσφέρει ένα υλικοτεχνικό και τεχνολογικό σχήμα που θα αυξήσει την παροχή ποιοτικής πρώτης ύλης για τη βελτιστοποίηση βιο-επεξεργασίας καθ' όλη τη διάρκεια ενός έτους.

Το Cluster Βιοοικονομίας και Περιβάλλοντος Δυτικής Μακεδονίας (Clube), φορέας με πολύ μεγάλη διαχειριστική εμπειρία σε αντίστοιχα έργα, αποτελεί τον κύριο εταίρο του έργου στη Δυτική Μακεδονία. Το ακόμα πιο ενδιαφέρον για το Clube, είναι το ότι πέτυχε να ανατεθεί το ένα από τα δύο ψηφιακά δίδυμα του έργου, στον Αγροτικό Συνεταιρισμό Βελβεντού ΔΗΜΗΤΡΑ που επίσης συμμετέχει ως εταίρος στο έργο. Έτσι ο Συνεταιρισμός θα έχει τη δυνατότητα να «δοκιμάσει» και φυσικά να βελτιστοποιήσει τις

διαδικασίες του σε ένα ιδιαίτερα καινοτόμο πρότζεκτ με ευρωπαϊκό μανδύα. Παράλληλα, θα έχει το ΕΚΕΤΑ ως δικό του «Τρίτο Διασυνδεδεμένο μέλος», για να το υποστηρίξει στα ερευνητικά ζητήματα και ειδικότερα στις αναλύσεις που θα χρειαστεί να γίνουν.

Το CIuBE εκτός από το συντονισμό των Ελλήνων Εταίρων, θα ηγηθεί και του πακέτου εργασίας 6, κύριος στόχος του οποίου είναι να ταιριάζει τις ειδικές απαιτήσεις της αγροδιατροφικής αξίας με τις δυνατότητες των ψηφιακών εργαλείων BBTWINS που θα αναπτυχθούν και να επαληθεύσει στο πεδίο τα δεδομένα. Θα επικεντρωθεί στη δοκιμή και την επικύρωση των προϊόντων σε πραγματικά περιβάλλοντα, για να διασφαλιστεί ότι πληρούνται οι απαιτήσεις των τελικών χρηστών και ότι η συμμόρφωση με αυτές τις απαιτήσεις επαληθεύεται από τις πιλοτικές περιπτώσεις.

This press release can be found on: <https://e-ptolemeos.gr/bbtwins-pos-tha-ginoyn-pio-apotelesmatika-kai-paragogika-ta-systimata-paragogis-trofimon-en-meso-tis-ayxanomenis-zitisis-pagkosmios/>

Press release

Digital twins promise resource efficiency for EU agri-food sector

Horizon 2020 project BBTWINS will apply cutting edge technology to optimise meat and fruit value chains

Brussels, 30 September 2021 – The EU agri-food sector is a key contributor to the European economy. Small company losses and inefficiencies in this sector accumulate, resulting in significant economic and environmental burdens. [Agriculture accounts for nearly one-third of all greenhouse gases \(GHG\)](#) and with the world population estimated to reach 10 billion by 2050, the system efficiencies of crop and livestock production must increase by 40% to meet this demand. Cutting edge technology presents an opportunity to advance the sector's sustainability through increasing efficiency and optimising value chains, helping to overcome these challenges.

[BBTWINS](#), a Bio-Based Industries Research and Innovation Action project, has received €4.7 million with the aim of reforming the sector. The project will contribute to the EU's [Farm-to-Fork strategy](#), a key component of the [EU Green Deal](#), by developing **digital twins** or digital representations of agricultural value-chains to increase resource efficiency, reduce waste and enable a more resilient agri-food sector.

Coordinated by CTIC-CITA, BBTWINS will run for four years (2021-2025) with 13 partners from seven countries including research organisations, cooperatives, bioeconomy clusters and businesses – working together to optimise the food value chain.

“The digitalisation of production processes is a powerful tool that will let us simulate different scenarios in a computer to identify improvements that really matter.”

– Daniel de la Puente, Senior EU Project Manager, CTIC-CITA

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Figure 10 Press release in Polish¹

Figure 11 Press release in Polish²

¹ In Poland most of the target audience is expected to speak , so the first part of the press release remains in the main language. An updated version of this press release (fully in Polish) maybe issued in the coming months before D8.15

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PRESS RELEASE

Słowa kluczowe

Cyfrowe bliźniaki, blockchain, logistyka, waloryzacja biomasy, czujniki, symulacja, nawozy, białka, przetwórstwo owoców, przetwórstwo mięsa, surowce, sole, białko, przekąski, nutraceutyki, odpady

O projekcie BBTWINS

Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) ma na celu opracowanie cyfrowej platformy do optymalizacji procesów w łańcuchu wartości w sektorze rolnictwie i żywności, oraz dostarczania wysokiej jakości biomasy do bioprzetwarzania.

Platforma będzie oparta na technologii „cyfrowych bliźniaków” – tworząc w czasie rzeczywistym cyfrową replikę fizycznych procesów w przemyśle rolno-spożywczym. BBTWINS połączy również sztuczną inteligencję (AI), uczenie maszynowe, Internet rzeczy (IoT) i analitykę oprogramowania na tej jednej platformie.

Wraz z 13 partnerami z 7 krajów, konsorcjum BBTWINS skoncentruje się na produkcji mięsa i owoców, integrując łańcuch wartości (od uprawy do produktu końcowego) i określi optymalną ścieżkę dla każdego surowca, aby zmaksymalizować wydajność i zminimalizować straty – bez wpływu na jakość.

Kontakt z mediami

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Figure 12 Press release in Polish